

Probing Soil Corrosivity Potential Using Barnes Geo-Electric Method in Shagamu, Southwestern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Corrosion of pipeline and other underground infrastructures are notable soil structure interaction process that have resulted in material and underground structural failures posing serious threat to the integrity of structures and safe movement of petroleum products. This paper presents the results of soil corrosivity evaluation using the Electrical Resistivity Test (Barnes Layer Analysis) and conventional Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) deploying Wenner and Schlumberger array systems respectively along buried pipelines routes in Shagamu, Southwestern, Nigeria. The investigation was carried out along six traverses in twenty different locations in N-S and E-W directions using resistivity meter. The resistivity distribution style at the probed depths pinpointed three distinct groups. Group 1, 2 and 3 have resistivity values which ranges between 50 – 100 ohm-m, 100 – 200 ohm-m and above 200 ohm-m respectively. The VES results however reveals three to five geo-electric layers which varies from topsoil, clay, clayey sand, sandy clayey sand and lateritic clayey sand. Interpretation of the ERT results and the generated iso-resistivity maps denote that the resistivity values of soils at depth range of 2.25 – 4.5m are lower compared to the resistivity at depth range of 0.75 – 1.5m which make depth range 2.25-4.5m a more corrosive environment. The iso-resistivity maps also reveal the order of resistivity signatures as $ERT@3.0m < ERT@4.50m < ERT@2.25m < ERT@0.75-1.50m$. Further analysis of the results shows that about 12.5% of the ERT points conducted reveals high corrosive probability, 35.5% indicates low corrosive probability and 51.0% reveals negligible corrosive probability across the study area in both N-S and E-W directions. Comparing the resistivity distribution styles along the various traverses indicate that the degree of vulnerability to corrosion can be arranged as $traverse\ 3 > traverse\ 4 > traverse\ 5 > traverse\ 6$, thereby pinpointing focus areas for possible treatments and rehabilitation. The capability of the Barnes analysis approach to delineate probable corrosion stretch along buried pipeline route demonstrate its effectiveness as a non-invasive corrosion evaluation tool.

KEYWORDS: Soil Corrosivity, Barnes Analysis, Electrical Method, Shagamu, Nigeria, Tomography, Iso-Resistivity

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I. INTRODUCTION

Pipeline and other engineering structures conveying petroleum and its associated products are critical civil infrastructures and the corrosion of these facilities when buried beneath the ground surface may result in severe environmental disaster. Corrosion of steel is a crucial problem for the construction industry since it poses the most serious risk to the structural integrity of reinforced concrete structures (Sagna and Jeena, 2020). Even though pipelines and associated reinforced concrete structures possess high strength and ductility, they often become thermodynamically unstable and oxidize (corrode) to a more stable state when they are buried beneath the ground and exposed to ambient environment (Parasnis, 1986). Therefore, subsurface soils corrosivity poses serious threat to the integrity of buried pipeline and other underground reinforced concrete structures. Corrosion which is an electron removal process from a metal and the subsequent acceptance of the released electrons by some other reduction reaction in the presence of oxygen and water is of particular interest in petroleum industry. Among various corrosion techniques, differential corrosion of cell is responsible for pipeline degradation (Kenneth and Godwin, 2013). This process occurring in soil is a major concern particularly for buried aging infrastructures. These necessitated the need to assess the level of soil corrosivity for both new and existing buried civil structures, failure to do so may lead to overestimation of the lifespan of the structure as well as jeopardising public safety with adverse effects on the environment should an accident occurs.

The corrosion of buried steel structures in soil are dictated by factors which includes redox potential, resistivity, soluble ion concentration, pH, water content and microbial activities (Lim *et al.*, 2013). The most critical components in the manufacturing of pipeline are carbon steel and cast iron alloys. These engineering materials are vulnerable to corrosion with the oxidation of metallic iron resulting in upto 600% increase in the original volume of iron (Tuuti, 1982) with substantial potential to encourage propagation of micro cracks and internal voids (Avedano and Ortega, 2011) thereby accelerating moisture entry into underground structures. In order to significantly reduce the high cost associated with rehabilitating corroded infrastructures, it is important to place premium on deploying effective ways to maintain existing underground infrastructures having corrosion issues so as to prolong their service life while ensuring adequate integrity.

This could be done by evaluating the conditions of the subsurface soil sequence which is in constant interaction with underground structures. Since corrosion is an electrochemical process aided by current flow, the electrochemical behaviours of soil are of fundamental considerations when assessing soil corrosivity potential. The degree of soil corrosivity can be evaluated by both laboratory and field based procedures. The laboratory methods are usually employed prior to the installation of the underground facilities while the field based procedure are often in form of Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) which assist in post mortem analysis of already constructed infrastructures. The NDT method is more suitable for the present studies because it is an existing infrastructure. The NDT methods often deployed for soil corrosivity delineation includes electrical resistivity and ground-penetrating radar (GPR). The GPR application though provides qualitative analysis of corrosion damage is limited by its high cost, advance instrumentation and sophisticated interpretation procedures. However, the electrical resistivity method is favoured due to its low cost, quick measurement time frame, and simple procedures during laboratory and field applications (Cheng *et al.*, 2014; Minagawa and Hisada, 2013; Spragg *et al.*, 2012). The electrical resistivity method has been widely used to investigate soil corrosivity for infrastructural developments (Faseki *et al.*, 2022; Edeye and Ette, 2021; Adeoti 2018; Oki *et al.*, 2016; Bhattarai 2013; Gopal 2010). The method has the capability to delineate soil resistivity along the length of pipeline thereby aiding the discrimination of corrosive zones. Therefore, for facilities such as pipelines and associated reinforced concrete structures, the potential classification of corrosion potential based on the absolute value of soil resistivity is needed. For the purpose of this study, the combination of Barnes and conventional Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) geo-electric method of geophysics was used for estimating lateral and vertical variations of resistivity along the

path of the oil pipeline, which was buried within the top 4.5m in NNPC/PPMC Depot Mosimi, Shagamu, Southwestern Nigeria to delineate potential corrosive zones.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

A. LOCATION AND GEOLOGY OF THE STUDY AREA

The study area is located at NNPC-PPMC, Mosimi Depot, Shagamu, Shagamu Local Government Area, Ogun State, Southwestern Nigeria (figure 1). It is accessible through Ikorodu – Shagamu road. It lies between longitude E 003°32'55.679 " to E 003°33'10.0" and latitude N 06°45'0.00" to N 06°45'15.01". The elevation varies between 84.4 to 120 m above the sea level. It is situated within the Eastern Dahomey Basin (Billman 1976). The Basin is one of the sedimentary basins on the continental margin of the Gulf of Guinea extending southeasterly from Ghana to the Western flank of the Niger Delta (Adeniran, 2015). The Basin is divided into the Northern and Southern zones (Okosun, 1990). The stratigraphy sequence spans from Cretaceous to Recent (figure 2) and the succession started with the Abeokuta group, comprising of the Ise formation overlying the basement complex, followed by the Araromi formation and terminating at the Cretaceous with the Afowo formation, a coarse to medium-grained sandstone, as the youngest sediment (Minapuye, et al., 2018). The Cretaceous Abeokuta group comprises Ise, Afowo, and the Araromi formation, the Paleocene Ewekoro formation; the late Paleocene to early Eocene Akinbo formation; the Eocene Oshosun and Ilaro formations and the Pleistocene to Benin formation (Adekeye 2005; Omatsola and Adegoke, 1981, Billman 1976). The surficial geology of the study area is composed of sediments that are typical of the marine environments, which is the intercalation of sand and clay interbedded with sandy clay, clayey sand, silt and peat. These sediments also grade into one another and vary widely in both lateral extent and thickness, they serve as the host for engineering infrastructures in the area.

Figure 1: Geological Map of Lagos and Ogun State Showing the Study Area ((Modified after Billman, 1976)

Figure 2: Stratigraphic column of the eastern Dahomey Basin (MSMD, 2006)

B. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Twenty (20) Electrical Resistivity Test (ERT) and Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) points data applying Wenner and Schlumberger arrays system respectively were obtained using PASI resistivity meter. The ERT was conducted along two orthogonal lines in the north-south (N-S) and east-west (E-W) directions to have a proper view of the subsurface resistivity distribution (figure 3).

Figure 3: Base Map of the Study Area

The tests were carried out in accordance with relevant ASTM standard (ASTM, 2001). The soil resistance was determined at depths of 0.75, 1.50, 2.25, 3.0 and 4.50 m in both North – South and East – West directions. For the VES data acquisition, the maximum depth probed was approximately 25.0m. The acquired apparent resistivity data were processed both quantitatively and qualitatively. The quantitative interpretation of the depth sounding curves was carried out using the partial curve matching technique (Bhattacharya and Patra, 1968). The true resistivity of the successive strata underneath each VES point was obtained using one-dimensional resistivity inversion carried out using Winresist software program. The corrosive rating was done using the generally accepted criteria (Gopal, 2010; Bhattarai, 2013). The Barnes geo-electric analysis deploying equation 1 and 2 below was used in the layer analysis (Ronald, 2001).

$$\rho_{layer} = 2\pi a \frac{V}{I} = 2\pi a R_{layer} \dots\dots\dots (i)$$

ρ_{layer} = layer resistivity; a is the electrode spacing = $a_2 - a_1$;

a_1 = upper electrode spacing; a_2 = immediate underlying lower electrode spacing

$$R_{layer} = R_1 \times R_2 / (R_1 - R_2) \dots\dots\dots (ii)$$

R_1 = Resistance of the upper layer; R_2 = Resistance of the immediate underlying lower layer

C. Results and Discussion

C.1 Barnes Layer Analysis

The summary of all the ERT points probed is presented in table 1 while the histogram and Iso- Resistivity maps are as shown in figures 4a – 4b and 5a – 9b respectively. All the soil resistivity tests conducted in N – S and E –W directions at depths of 0.75, 1.50, 2.25, 3 and 4.50 m ranges from 50 to 2011 ohm-m (table 1), these resistivity values fall within high to negligible corrosive probability boundary (Gopal, 2010). The resistivity distribution style at the stated depths pinpointed three distinct groups. Group 1, 2 and 3 have resistivity values which ranges between 50 – 100 ohm-m, 100 – 200 ohm-m and above 200 ohm-m respectively. At depth range 0.75 – 1.50m, the test returns resistivity values above 200 ohm-m indicating negligible corrosive probability across the layer except for ERT 1 and 2 which shows low corrosive probability at N-S direction only. Also, at depth 1.50 – 2.25m, ERT 11, 13, 19 in E – W and ERT 2,11, 14, 15, 16 and 19 possesses negligible corrosive tendency.

It is noticeable that at 3.0m depth, ERT 1, 2 4, 5, 10, 12, 18 and 20 with resistivity value range of 50 – 100 ohm-m fall within high corrosive probability zone in the E –W direction while 2, 4, 10, 15 and 18 indicate area of high corrosive probability in the N – S direction (table 1). Careful observation further shows that ERT 2, 4, 10 and 18 denote corrosion zones in both directions showing the close similarity in the results. Further perusal of the results at 4.50m depth show that ERT 3, 6, 8, 10 and 16 as well as ERT 4, 6,8,9, and 12 are diagnostic of high corrosion zones in E – W and N – S direction respectively. This is suggestive that high corrosion zone is along the 3.0 – 4.50m layer and this is the area where rehabilitation efforts should be concentrated. From the histogram graphs plotted for both N-S and E-W direction (figures 4a – 4b), it is obvious that at depth range of 2.25 – 4.5m, the resistivity values are lower compared to the resistivity at a depth range of 0.75 – 1.5m which make depth range of 2.25-4.5m a more corrosive environment. Also, a careful look at the iso-resistivity maps generated across the area reveals the order of resistivity signatures as $ERT@3.0m < ERT@4.50m < ERT@2.25m < ERT@0.75-1.50m$, this clearly implicated the soil at depth range of 2.25 – 4.50m as being more corrosive in both E –W and N –S directions than those at depth range of 0.75 – 1.50m

which generally indicates negligible corrosive potential (5a – 9b). The iso-resistivity maps generated for depth 0.75m and 1.50m (figures 5a – 6b) clearly shows that the zone possess low to negligible corrosivity potential while the maps for depths 3.0m and 4.0m pinpointed high corrosion zone. Only small portion of the length probed at depth 2.25m exemplifies by ERT 2 and 10 in E – W direction falls on the high corrosion zone. Further interpretation of the results shows that about 12.5% of the ERT points conducted reveals high corrosive probability, 35.5% also indicates low corrosive probability and 51.0% reveals negligible corrosive probability across the study area in both N-S and E-W. Exploring the relationship between the resistivity distribution pattern and the traverse lines shows (figure 3) that the high corrosivity portion is concentrated along traverses 3 and 4. This is because ERT 1, 2, 4 and 5 at depth 3.0m designated as corrosion belt are along traverse 3 while ERT 6, 8, 9 and 10 at depth of 4.50m which is also a corrosive stretch are along traverse 4. Based on these observations, the degree of corrosivity potential order can be put as traverse 3>traverse 4>traverse 5>traverse 6, thereby pinpointing focus areas for possible treatment and rehabilitation.

Table 1: Soil Resistivity Test Results for Barnes Method

ERT NO	Depth (m)	Resistivity (Ω m)		Layer (m)	Layer Resistivity (Ω m)		Corrosion	
		N – S	E – W		N – S	E – W	Probability	
							N – S	E – W
1	0.75	163.4891	226.6232	0.0-0.75	163.4891	226.6232	Low	Negligible
	1.5	268.5555	261.9594	0.75-1.5	751.5222	310.3509	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	228.9789	214.8444	1.5-2.25	176.8536	158.0073	Low	Low
	3	179.037	146.9988	2.25-3.0	108.2239	75.48587	Low	High
	4.5	183.7485	138.5181	3.0-4.5	193.9568	124.1886	Low	Low
2	0.75	172.9121	266.1998	0.0-0.75	172.9121	266.1998	Low	Negligible
	1.5	305.3052	274.2093	0.75-1.5	1302.872	282.7158	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	261.4883	251.2392	1.5-2.25	203.1707	79.72933	Negligible	High
	3	128.1528	111.1914	2.25-3.0	50.65869	61.96604	High	High
	4.5	127.2105	110.2491	3.0-4.5	125.3669	108.4116	Low	Low
3	0.75	315.1994	301.536	0.0-0.75	315.1994	301.536	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	284.5746	355.2471	0.75-1.5	259.3739	432.2398	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	230.3924	209.1906	1.5-2.25	166.8549	114.796	Low	Low
	3	188.46	235.575	2.25-3.0	121.9007	378.9685	Low	Negligible
	4.5	163.9602	135.6912	3.0-4.5	130.1271	73.42597	Low	High
4	0.75	294.4688	306.7187	0.0-0.75	294.4688	306.7187	Negligible	Negligible

	1.5	267.6132	371.2662	0.75-1.5	245.2467	470.2224	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	210.6041	204.9503	1.5-2.25	147.6828	108.0996	Low	Low
	3	163.9602	126.2682	2.25-3.0	98.50835	58.68234	High	High
	4.5	121.5567	135.6912	3.0-4.5	80.11692	159.4967	High	Low
5	0.75	213.9021	221.9117	0.0-0.75	213.9021	221.9117	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	230.8635	252.5364	0.75-1.5	250.7465	292.9671	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	193.6427	196.4696	1.5-2.25	146.4273	136.0564	Low	Low
	3	184.6908	133.8066	2.25-3.0	162.1964	68.37911	Low	High
	4.5	152.6526	135.6912	3.0-4.5	113.333	139.6243	Low	Low
6	0.75	266.1998	334.9877	0.0-0.75	266.1998	334.9877	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	274.2093	295.8822	0.75-1.5	282.7158	264.9524	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	204.9503	203.5368	1.5-2.25	136.1656	125.3148	Low	Low
	3	175.2678	201.6522	2.25-3.0	122.1819	196.2021	Low	Low
	4.5	127.2105	135.6912	3.0-4.5	82.15678	82.02801	High	High
7	0.75	257.2479	342.5261	0.0-0.75	257.2479	342.5261	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	302.4783	307.1898	0.75-1.5	381.1946	278.4626	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	214.8444	213.431	1.5-2.25	134.336	132.5305	Low	Low
	3	190.3446	205.4214	2.25-3.0	181.5352	184.6347	Low	Low
	4.5	158.3064	161.1333	3.0-4.5	118.4366	112.5867	Low	Low
8	0.75	356.1894	327.4493	0.0-0.75	356.1894	327.4493	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	316.6128	316.6128	0.75-1.5	284.9515	494.1292	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	230.3924	230.3924	1.5-2.25	149.1557	131.0323	Low	Low
	3	188.46	184.6908	2.25-3.0	121.9007	111.7513	Low	Low
	4.5	127.2105	130.0374	3.0-4.5	77.09727	81.69016	High	High
9	0.75	345.8241	324.6224	0.0-0.75	345.8241	324.6224	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	305.3052	361.8432	0.75-1.5	273.2854	408.7049	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	251.5941	253.0076	1.5-2.25	186.1107	157.9754	Low	Low
	3	209.1906	205.4214	2.25-3.0	138.94	131.323	Low	Low
	4.5	152.6526	155.4795	3.0-4.5	99.09028	104.6128	High	Low
10	0.75	302.9495	306.7187	0.0-0.75	302.9495	306.7187	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	261.9594	261.9594	0.75-1.5	230.7396	228.6	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	195.0561	169.614	1.5-2.25	129.1086	99.47825	Low	High

	3	145.1142	133.8066	2.25-3.0	82.07279	81.92241	High	High
	4.5	161.1333	113.076	3.0-4.5	206.7877	86.32684	Negligible	High
11	0.75	368.9105	303.8918	0.0-0.75	368.9105	303.8918	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	310.0167	287.4015	0.75-1.5	267.3382	272.6088	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	288.3438	359.0163	1.5-2.25	252.9736	715.6861	Negligible	Negligible
	3	284.5746	346.7664	2.25-3.0	273.8359	314.5667	Negligible	Negligible
	4.5	277.0362	268.5555	3.0-4.5	263.0973	185.072	Negligible	Low
12	0.75	423.0927	407.0736	0.0-0.75	423.0927	407.0736	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	323.2089	293.9976	0.75-1.5	261.4789	230.0851	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	233.2193	237.4596	1.5-2.25	149.8019	171.4986	Low	Low
	3	192.2292	165.8448	2.25-3.0	125.8644	87.06852	Low	High
	4.5	144.1719	189.4023	3.0-4.5	96.1146	264.5619	High	Negligible
13	0.75	361.8432	373.622	0.0-0.75	361.8432	373.622	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	342.0549	396.7083	0.75-1.5	324.3187	422.8356	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	261.4883	303.8918	1.5-2.25	177.7532	207.0201	Low	Negligible
	3	160.191	188.46	2.25-3.0	74.08834	88.08457	Low	Low
	4.5	149.8257	206.3637	3.0-4.5	132.6582	254.77	Low	Negligible
14	0.75	397.1795	373.622	0.0-0.75	397.1795	373.622	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	663.3792	503.1882	0.75-1.5	2011.614	770.3248	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	481.9865	302.4783	1.5-2.25	311.5872	168.2536	Negligible	Low
	3	341.1126	309.0744	2.25-3.0	181.7491	330.7096	Low	Negligible
	4.5	260.0748	285.5169	3.0-4.5	176.3054	247.7501	Low	Negligible
15	0.75	342.9972	308.1321	0.0-0.75	342.9972	308.1321	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	509.7843	323.2089	0.75-1.5	992.3074	339.837	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	415.5543	217.6713	1.5-2.25	303.3939	131.6777	Negligible	Low
	3	222.3828	235.575	2.25-3.0	92.87009	312.7461	High	Negligible
	4.5	189.4023	240.2865	3.0-4.5	146.075	250.2984	Low	Negligible
16	0.75	295.8822	308.6033	0.0-0.75	295.8822	308.6033	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	302.4783	277.9785	0.75-1.5	309.3752	252.8832	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	258.6614	227.5655	1.5-2.25	200.5563	166.9945	Negligible	Low
	3	273.267	192.2292	2.25-3.0	328.9991	131.1394	Negligible	Low
	4.5	183.7485	132.8643	3.0-4.5	111.0147	82.13429	Low	High

17	0.75	345.8241	397.1795	0.0-0.75	345.8241	397.1795	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	341.1126	307.1898	0.75-1.5	336.5278	250.4458	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	231.8058	224.7386	1.5-2.25	141.2689	146.2371	Low	Low
	3	177.1524	224.2674	2.25-3.0	103.7607	222.8657	Low	Negligible
	4.5	144.1719	161.1333	3.0-4.5	105.0555	103.0907	Low	Low
18	0.75	257.2479	289.7573	0.0-0.75	257.2479	289.7573	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	388.2276	475.8615	0.75-1.5	790.9413	1330.249	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	275.6228	230.3924	1.5-2.25	174.4341	113.3997	Low	Low
	3	165.8448	190.3446	2.25-3.0	75.56013	50.72951	High	High
	4.5	149.8257	192.2292	3.0-4.5	125.5682	196.1126	Low	Low
19	0.75	396.2372	412.7274	0.0-0.75	396.2372	412.7274	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	492.8229	466.4385	0.75-1.5	651.673	536.2206	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	402.8333	426.8619	1.5-2.25	295.0725	364.9337	Negligible	Negligible
	3	329.805	297.7668	2.25-3.0	213.6237	156.1208	Negligible	Low
	4.5	149.8257	305.3052	3.0-4.5	209.8759	321.5881	Negligible	Negligible
20	0.75	305.7764	311.9013	0.0-0.75	305.7764	311.9013	Negligible	Negligible
	1.5	293.9976	327.9204	0.75-1.5	283.0926	345.6741	Negligible	Negligible
	2.25	233.2193	261.4883	1.5-2.25	164.9987	186.0898	Low	Low
	3	209.1906	180.9216	2.25-3.0	159.7984	94.01825	Low	High
	4.5	206.3637	149.8257	3.0-4.5	200.9331	111.4982	Negligible	Low

Figure 4a: Histogram showing resistivity variation with depth in the N-S Direction

Figure 4b: Histogram showing resistivity variation with depth in the E-W Direction.

Figure 5a: Iso-Resistivity map at depth 0.75m showing resistivity distribution in E-W direction

Figure 5b: Iso-Resistivity map at depth 0.75m showing resistivity distribution in N-S direction

Figure 6a: Iso-Resistivity map at depth 1.50m showing resistivity distribution in E-W direction

Figure 6b: Iso-Resistivity map at depth 1.50m showing resistivity distribution in N-S direction

Figure 7a: Iso-Resistivity map at depth 2.25m showing resistivity distribution in E-W direction

Figure 7b: Iso-Resistivity map at depth 2.25m showing resistivity distribution in N-S direction

Figure 8a: Iso-Resistivity map at depth 3.0m showing resistivity distribution in E-W direction

Figure 8b: Iso-Resistivity map at depth 3.0m showing resistivity distribution in N-S direction

Figure 9a: Iso-Resistivity map at depth 4.5m showing resistivity distribution in E-W direction

Figure 9b: Iso-Resistivity map at depth 4.5m showing resistivity distribution in N-S direction

C.2 Vertical Electrical Sounding

A summary of the interpreted VES results with inferred lithology is as presented in table 2 while samples of the derived VES curves are shown in figures 10a – 10b. The table reveals three to five geo-electric layers which varies from topsoil, clay, clayey sand, sandy clayey sand and lateritic clayey sand. The topsoil corresponding to a depth range of 0.3 – 0.8 m has a resistivity range of 169.9 – 1558.8Ωm. The relatively higher values of resistivity indicate dry soils and the presence of lateilized clayey sand. Thus at the depth range 0.0 – 0.75m, the subsurface has a low to negligible corrosive effect on any buried pipeline within this subsurface horizon (Gopal, 2010). The second unit compose of clay, sandy clay and clayey sand within a depth range of 1.9-9.0 m having resistivity values ranging from 69.2 – 186 ohm-m suggesting high to low corrosive probability. The third geo-electric unit denote clay, sand and lateritic clayey sand with resistivity and layer thickness values ranging from 23.7 – 2449.8 ohm-m and 2.9 – 20.6 m respectively and a depth range of 4.0 – 27.8m indicating high to negligible corrosion

probability across the study area. These corroborate the results of the Barnes layer analysis which implicated soil at depth range of 2.25 – 4.0m as being corrosive, denoting that the corrosive layers are essentially clayey in nature. The fourth horizon beneath VES (3,4,16 to 20) is diagnostic of sand and lateritic clayey sand with resistivity values ranging from 393.6 to 5249.7 ohm-m while that beneath VES (6 to 10 and 11) is representative of clay and sandy clay with resistivity values ranging from 47.8 to 136.5 ohm-m having layer thickness that could not be determined because current terminated at that point. The fifth substratum layer beneath VES (1, 2 13 to 15) is indicative of sand and lateritic clayey sand with resistivity values ranging from 206.5 to 1000.5 ohm-m indicating negligible corrosive probability except VES 12 with resistivity value of 140.8Ωm but these layers were not considered for the purpose of corrosion probability assessment due to their deeper depth.

Figure 10a: Resistivity Curve of VES 1

Figure 10b: Resistivity Curve of VES 10

Table 2: Summary of the Interpreted VES Results with Inferred Lithology

VES No	LAYERS	RESISTIVITY (Ωm)	THICKNESS (m)	DEPTH (m)	LITHOLOGY
1	1	430.3	0.6	0.6	Topsoil
	2	109.8	1.6	2.2	Sandy Clay
	3	76.2	11.2	13.5	Clay
	4	338.8	9.0	22.5	Sand
	5	5069.1	---	---	Lateritic Clayey Sand
2	1	988.5	0.5	0.5	Topsoil
	2	139.6	0.8	1.2	Sandy Clay
	3	83.6	3.8	5.0	Clay
	4	3574.5	13.0	18	Lateritic Clayey Sand
	5	10005	---	---	Lateritic Clayey Sand
3	1	169.9	0.5	0.5	Topsoil
	2	115.2	7.4	8.0	Sandy Clay
	3	23.7	12.4	20.4	Clay
	4	5249.7	---	---	Lateritic Clayey Sand
4	1	391	0.6	0.6	Topsoil
	2	90.1	6.5	7.1	Clay
	3	455.2	20.6	27.8	Sand
	4	633.7	---	--	Sand
5	1	353.8	0.4	0.4	Topsoil
	2	159.3	9.1	9.4	Clayey Sand
	3	446.4	---	---	Sand
6	1	819.6	0.4	0.6	Topsoil
	2	98.0	1.5	1.9	Clay
	3	2172.9	7.8	9.7	Lateritic Clayey Sand
	4	71.2	---	---	Clay
7	1	503.8	0.4	0.4	Topsoil
	2	136.5	1.9	2.3	Sandy Clay
	3	2061	8.5	10.9	Lateritic Clayey Sand
	4	76.0	---	---	Clay
8	1	1107.6	0.3	0.3	Topsoil
	2	69.8	1.8	2.1	Clay

	3	1813.4	5.7	7.8	Lateritic Clayey Sand
	4	47.2	---	---	Clay
9	1	716.3	0.3	0.8	Topsoil
	2	64.9	1.5	2.3	Clay
	3	2392	6.4	8.72	Lateritic Clayey Sand
	4	98.1	---	---	Clay
10	1	578.4	0.4	0.4	Topsoil
	2	160.0	3.5	4.0	Clayey Sand
	3	842.4	14.9	18.8	Sand
	4	107	---	---	Sandy Clay
11	1	416.6	0.5	0.5	Topsoil
	2	158.0	2.3	2.7	Clayey Sand
	3	620	7.3	10.1	Sand
	4	127.7	---	---	Sandy Clay
12	1	467.8	0.4	0.3	Topsoil
	2	124.6	2.2	2.6	Sandy Clay
	3	1849.1	1.4	4.0	Lateritic Clayey Sand
	4	76.3	11.0	15.0	Clay
	5	140.8	---	---	Sandy Clay
13	1	953.4	0.4	0.4	Topsoil
	2	69.2	1.0	1.4	Clay
	3	720.0	4.2	5.7	Sand
	4	77.8	21.4	27.0	Clay
	5	296.4	---	---	Clayey Sand
14	1	557.0	0.4	0.4	Topsoil
	2	93.6	1.5	1.9	Clay
	3	1076.9	2.9	4.8	Lateritic Clayey Sand
	4	54.6	10	14.7	Clay
	5	206.1	---	---	Clayey Sand
15	1	640.5	0.4	0.4	Topsoil
	2	92.6	1.5	1.9	Clay
	3	938.1	3.4	5.2	Sand
	4	57.6	12.9	18.1	Clay
	5	245.5	---	---	Clayey Sand
16	1	1033.3	0.6	0.6	Topsoil

	2	119.3	2.4	2.8	Sandy Clay
	3	2449.8	5.3	9.1	Lateritic Clayey Sand
	4	501.5	---	---	Sand
17	1	1062.7	0.4	0.4	Topsoil
	2	87.2	1.8	2.3	Clay
	3	2177.7	9.6	11.9	Lateritic Clayey Sand
	4	393.6	---	---	Sand
18	1	1197	0.6	0.6	Topsoil
	2	186.3	3.4	4.0	Clayey Sand
	3	1674.0	10.2	14.2	Lateritic Clayey Sand
	4	453.4	---	---	Clayey Sand
19	1	1736.3	0.7	0.7	Topsoil
	2	128.8	1.9	2.5	Sandy Clay
	3	983.5	15.7	18.2	Sand
	4	560.4	---	---	Sand
20	1	1558.8	0.8	0.8	Topsoil
	2	90.0	1.3	2.1	Clay
	3	577.2	16.7	18.8	Sand
	4	963.1	---	---	Sand

III. CONCLUSION

- ✓ Soil Corrosion evaluation deploying Barnes layer analysis and Vertical Electrical Sounding method of geophysical interpretation has been conducted in six traverses along buried pipeline routes within NNPC – PPMC, Mosimi Depot, Shagamu, Nigeria. The results of ERT in N–S and E–W directions shows that the resistivity value ranges from 50 – 2011 ohm-m which falls within high to negligible corrosive probability;
- ✓ From the ERT results, it is observed that at depth range of 2.25 – 4.5m, the resistivity values are lower compared to the resistivity at a depth range of 0.75 – 1.5m which make depth range of 2.25-4.5m a more corrosive environment. Also, the VES results reveal that area corresponding to high corrosive horizons are lithologically clayey in nature;
- ✓ Interpretation of the results further show that about 12.5% of the ERT points conducted reveals high corrosive probability, 35.5% indicates low corrosive probability and 51.0% reveals negligible corrosive probability across the study area in both N-S and E-W;
- ✓ Based on the results, the degree of corrosivity potential order can be put as traverse 3>traverse 4>traverse 5>traverse 6, thereby pinpointing focus areas for possible treatments and rehabilitation.
- ✓ These thereby suggest that the Barnes layer analysis approach is an effective method of non-invasively delineating corrosion zones along buried civil infrastructures.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest

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